

July. 2026, Tabriz, Iran

The Existential Levels of Architecture and Its Definition Based on Form, Spatial System, and Shape in Monotheistic Ontology

1- Athar Ebrahim Niafard 2- Houtan Irvani

1- Corresponding Author, PhD Student of Architecture, Ardestan Branch, Islamic Azad University of Isfahan Masuod.athar@gmail.com

2- Assistant Professor of Architecture, Ardestan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Faculty Member of Isfahan Water Studies Research Center Houtan.irvani@iau.ac.ir

Abstract

The definition of architecture has always been a controversial issue in the theoretical field of architecture, and most of the existing definitions, influenced by the historical, cultural, and theoretical contexts of each period, have reflected only part of its truth. This research, with a theoretical-analytical approach based on monotheistic ontology in the Iranian-Islamic tradition, explains the essence and truth of architecture and seeks to provide a comprehensive and inclusive definition of it. To this end, first, the common definitions of architecture are criticized and their conceptual shortcomings are examined. Then, relying on the analysis of fundamental existential concepts, three main levels in the formation of architecture are formulated: "form" as the space of ideas, meanings, and individual and collective beliefs; "spatial system" as the hidden structure that organizes human actions, relationships, and behaviors; and "shape" as the physical crystallization of architecture in the context of time, space, and technology. These levels are considered to correspond to the levels of human cognition - sense, imagination, and reason - and are interpreted within an epistemological framework that considers cognition to be the result of the empathic presence between perceiver and perceived. Accordingly, the present study proposes a definition of architecture that can be used both in reading and criticizing past and contemporary works, and in researching and producing architectural theory, composition, and design.

Keywords: What is architecture, monotheistic ontology, spatial system, existential levels, form, spatial system, shape.

July. 2026, Tabriz, Iran

1- Introduction:

The question of what architecture is and the need for a comprehensive definition

Explaining the “what” and “truth” of architecture, beyond the discussion of its “how,” has always been one of the most difficult theoretical issues in the field of architecture, and the scope of this field is so vast that it makes it difficult to achieve a precise and comprehensive definition. Architecture is a combination of “wanting” and “building” and can at the same time be the manifestation of mysticism and spirituality, the emergence of active man in the earthly world, or the manifestation of the supernatural in nature, and establish a link between truth and reality or be reduced to simply representing phenomena in formal forms. In each period, numerous definitions of architecture have been presented, each of which reflects only a part of its truth and emphasizes a specific aspect, appropriate to the spirit of the times (Taqwaei, 2010, p. 76).

Many famous definitions of architecture, such as “architecture is the art of space” (Bruno Zwi) or “architecture is crystallized music” (Goethe), rather than being timeless and comprehensive definitions, reflect the intellectual and cultural conditions of their time; for example, Zwi’s emphasis on space during the era of modern architecture and Einstein’s relativity, and Goethe’s emphasis on music in the context of European romanticism. While from a logical and philosophical perspective, a definition should express the “existential perfection of the essence” of an object and include all of its intrinsic predicates, actual or potential (Avicenna, 1366, p. 25). In “Al-Hudud”, Avicenna specifies that a definition should express the essence of an object in such a way that none of its intrinsic requirements are omitted; and contemporary logicians also emphasize their analytical role in revealing the contents and essences of a concept, in addition to the role of definitions in “discovering the unknown”. According to this view, the more the definition of architecture addresses its inherent truths and foundations, the more comprehensive and efficient it will be, and the more it will avoid falling into the trap of formal, sectional, and simplistic definitions (Khansari, 1999, p. 83; Kapen, 2004).

2. Theoretical Framework: Monotheistic Ontology and the Problem of Knowledge

2.1. Theoretical-Intuitive Approach and Monotheistic Ontology

The article does not rely solely on formal and empirical evidence, nor does it stop at the realm of abstract theorizing without epistemological support; rather, by adopting a “theoretical-intuitive” approach, it attempts to achieve a kind of “cognitive operating system” in the

July. 2026, Tabriz, Iran

creation and analysis of architecture that enables the meaning of sensory, rational, and intuitive perceptions. This operating system is here “monotheistic ontology” and the knowledge based on it; an approach that, inspired by the thought of thinkers whom Henry Corbin calls “Orientalists,” seeks to achieve timeless and spatial truths of architecture that are free from the constraints of sectional conditions (Grabar, 1992, p.231).

In this framework, architectural truths are sought in such a way that any human being, “going from the surface to the depth,” in any time and place, can reach them by entering from the surface to the interior. Therefore, relying on the legacy of Islamic-Iranian philosophy and mysticism is not simply due to historical affiliation, but also to overcome the dead ends of pure sciences and purely positivist approaches in understanding architecture (Taqvaei, 2010, p. 76).

2.2. Levels of cognition: Sense, imagination, reason

Given that architecture is both created and perceived by humans, the connection between the “levels of human cognition” and the “levels of architectural existence” becomes important. Mulla Sadra classifies the means of cognition into three levels of sense, imagination, and reason; a chain that connects different levels of perception, from the most tangible to the most abstract. This triad is the basis for understanding the relationship between sensory perceptions, imaginary forms, and conceptual reasoning in architectural perception (Sadr al-Mutalahin, 1974, p. 265).

In this view, each level of cognition opens up a specific realm of truth, and it is not possible to weigh claims related to the realm of imagination with the “scale of sense” or to test all claims solely by the criteria of empirical science. Modern Western philosophy has generally been content with sense and partial reason and has ignored "imagination" - especially "active imagination" - which in Islamic mysticism is the intermediary link between the knowledge of certainty, the reality of certainty, and the truth of certainty (Karbon, 1979; Shaygan, 1980, p. 386).

2.3. The Connection of Existence and Knowledge in Islamic Philosophy

In Islamic philosophy and mysticism, the truth of everything is considered to be its very existence; truth is the unfolding of existence, and existence has a long series of levels that all ultimately return to the Necessary Existence. In this intellectual system, knowledge is not only the result of mental representation, but is itself a type of existence; a point at which the existence of the perceiver and the perceived intersect. As a result, the knowledge of architecture is a kind of “empathetic presence” and “co-language” between man and the work, and the reality of architecture is only a part of its truth (Sadr al-Mutalaheen, 1366, p. 8; Mojtahidi, 1382, p. 6).

July. 2026, Tabriz, Iran

Accordingly, the means of knowledge (sense, imagination, reason) must all bear the burden of understanding architecture; an approach in which the architect and observer, not the owner, are “guests in the house of architecture” and sit next to the host (the architectural work). This empathetic presence is a condition for reaching deeper levels of architectural truth and moving beyond the merely physical and formal level (Taqwaei, 2010, p. 78).

3. Fundamental Existential Levels of Architecture

3.1. Characteristics of Fundamental Truths of Architecture

Taqvai establishes a set of criteria for extracting the “fundamental truths” of architecture. These truths must:

1. Represent the essence and truth of architecture before and after material crystallization;
2. Respond to the formal, conceptual, and functional dimensions of architecture;
3. Do not lead to dry and stereotyped instructions and patterns and open up the possibility of diversity;
4. Be independent, yet dependent and complementary to each other;
5. Their essence must remain stable in all temporal and spatial transformations (Flamaki, 2002).

These truths are first sought in the “world of imagination” and above that in the “general intellect”; where one end is in the divine essence and the other end is in the world of sense, and the “what” of things is embodied in that position before “what they are” and “how they are.” Then, the manner of their physical and formal manifestation is examined at lower levels (Taqwaei, 2010, p. 79).

To explain the relationship between fixed truth and multiple manifestations of architecture, the analogy of “red color” is used: the existential truth of architecture is like a transparent red sheet that, by passing through different temporal-spatial contexts (for example, Safavid Iran with yellow color, Ottoman with blue color), turns into combinations such as orange and purple, without losing its essence of being red. This article seeks to identify the components of this “red color of architecture” (Taqwaei, 2010, p. 79; Hojjat, cited in the same).

Ultimately, this “red color” manifests itself in three main levels of form, spatial system, and shape, which can be examined both separately and in the context of architecture as a whole (Taqwaei, 2010, p. 80).

July. 2026, Tabriz, Iran

3.2. First level: Form (idea, dream, belief)

“Form” is the most fundamental existential level of architecture and is related to the essence and “what-being” of the work. In different philosophical traditions, form has been explained by names such as Plato’s “Eidos”, Aristotle’s “Form of Type”, “Divine Thoughts”, “Fixed Objects” and in Mulla Sadra’s philosophy as the essence of existence. Form is the fixed and essential truth of things that belongs to reason, is eternal and eternal and can only be imitated or perceived through the material world (Pazuki, 1379, p. 62; Sadr al-Mutalahin, 1353, p. 94).

In Islamic philosophy, form is not simply the external appearance of the body, but also the “actuality and perfection” of something in that it was previously potential and imperfect. With the elimination of the distance between the perceiver and the perceived in the process of cognition, forms, which are themselves a type of existence, find their way into the human mind, and therefore, form in artistic creation precedes the specific object. The artist begins his work with “a word formed in his mind”; that is, an idea, dream, or inspiration that is capable of imitation and embodiment (Coomaraswamy, 2005, p. 324).

In architecture, form can be the manifestation of the architect’s mental “utopia,” individual and social beliefs, or the worldview that dominates an era. Ancient Egyptian architecture (the greatness of the pharaoh and immortality), holy cities such as Benares (the cycle of life and death), Safavid architecture (representing “there” in “here”), or architecture based on a contemporary cosmic perspective (a scientific-cosmic worldview), each express different forms that in advance direct the quality of the spatial system and form (Jenks, 2003).

3.3. Second Order: Spatial Order (Hidden Plan of Life)

The “spatial order” is the second order of architectural existence and the intermediary link between form (the rational order) and form (the tangible and physical order). This system is the “hidden plan” or the organizing structure of human life in space that regulates the musts and mustn’ts of movement, pause, seeing, hearing, and human interactions (Taqwaei, 2010, p. 82).

In connection with Louis Kahn’s thought, order is considered to be something more than mere material development; an order that makes the “being” of objects possible and gives space a “superior sense of presence”; a concept that is consistent with the “Tao” in Lao Tzu’s thought and “Being” in Heidegger’s. Architecture, in this sense, is the “container of human life” and the spatial system shapes the quality of organization of this container, in accordance with functions, habits, traditions and social relations (Schulz-Norberg, 1979).

This view distances itself from reductive functionalism - such as “form follows function” (Sullivan) or the reduction of architecture to a function of function and economy. In the architecture of the past of Iran, the hierarchical, central and axial spatial system in the

July. 2026, Tabriz, Iran

markets, central courtyards, fire temples and mosques is a manifestation of the contribution of Iranian-Islamic culture to this system; just as in modern architecture, the systems of “simultaneity of places” and “free plan” seek to reflect the principles of democracy and social equality (Ardalan et al., 1379; Ligo, 1984; Norberg-Schulz, 1381).

3.4. Third level: Form (physical crystallization)

“Form” is the third and most material level of architectural existence; the last external word of the architect that manifests the form and spatial system in the outside world. Form is bound by historical, geographical, cultural conditions, construction technology, materials, light and structure, and for this reason, the form of past periods cannot be repeated in the present era without paying attention to the temporal-spatial context. However, form is not simply an apparent shell, but a stage in which the answer to “what is” (form) and “how to organize life” (spatial system) is transformed into a tangible, experiential and critical form. From this perspective, every architectural form contains form and every original form inevitably leads to some kind of form-making. Form provides the possibility of comparing architectures, criticizing works and consciously designing new works (Taqvaei, 2010, p. 85).

4. A comprehensive definition of architecture based on three levels of existence

By summarizing the above three levels and explaining their relationship with the levels of human cognition, a comprehensive definition of architecture is proposed:

"Architecture is a form of dreams, individual beliefs, and social values, in a form (form) bound to construction technology and relying on the requirements of time and place, with architectural language and expression, that provides a "spatial system" for human life."

In this definition, the three key elements of architecture, including "form" (content and worldview), "form" (material crystallization and bound to conditions), and "spatial system" (organizing human life), are placed together in a dynamic connection. While maintaining a connection with the Iranian-Islamic philosophical and mystical tradition, this definition avoids reducing architecture to single dimensions such as form, function, or space, and has the capacity to simultaneously analyze past works and guide future designs (Taqvaei, 2010, p. 86).

4-1. The Third Dimension: Research and Theory Generation in Architecture

The important achievement of this redefinition is the expansion of the realm of architecture beyond “reading and criticism” or “construction and design.” Defining architecture based on

July. 2026, Tabriz, Iran

existential levels reveals the necessity of addressing the realm of research and theory generation. At this level, architecture is understood not simply as an object for analysis nor as a product for construction, but as a field for conceptual formulation and rethinking the relationship between man, space, and the world.

By relying on an understanding of existential levels (form, spatial system, and shape), architectural research provides the possibility of extracting fundamental concepts and critiquing common assumptions, leading to the production of sustainable theoretical frameworks that will serve as both the basis for critiquing existing works and guiding future designs. In this way, architecture goes beyond the level of a practical action or passive interpretation and is elevated to the realm of thought and meaning generation.

5. Conclusion: Theoretical and Practical Implications of a Comprehensive Definition of Architecture

By placing architecture within the framework of a monistic ontology and linking it to the levels of human cognition, architecture is considered not simply a product of performance, economy, or technique, but rather a manifestation of the existential relationship between man and the world at the three levels of form, spatial system, and shape. This approach allows us to move beyond sectional, formal definitions that are dependent on purely formal flows and leads us to truths that, despite having substantial stability, find multiple manifestations in different temporal and spatial contexts.

The proposed definition provides a conceptual tool for an integrated understanding of architecture in three basic areas:

- First, for reading and analyzing past and contemporary architecture through identifying form, spatial system, and shape;
- Second, for composing and designing contemporary architecture with awareness of the connection between worldview, spatial organization, and physical crystallization;
- And third, to research and produce architectural theory with the aim of explaining fundamental concepts and providing sustainable theoretical frameworks.

Accordingly, architecture is re-understood in relation to reality, not on a fashionable or merely physical level, but in its existential and human dimension. Such a definition, while creating a coherent foundation for the study and criticism of architectural works, opens up a new horizon for conscious and semantic design and at the same time provides the possibility of developing the theoretical system of architecture. Thus, architecture is not a phenomenon

July. 2026, Tabriz, Iran

dependent on fleeting tastes or external conditions, but rather something with meaning, explanatory ability and theoretical coherence; something that can play an active role in organizing human life simultaneously in the realm of theory and practice.

Reference

- [1] Grabar, O. (1992). *The mediation of ornament*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- [2] Ligo, L. L. (1984). *The concept of function in twentieth century architectural criticism*. Michigan: UMI Research Press.
- [3] Norberg-Schulz, C. (1979). Kahn, Heidegger and the language of architecture. *Oppositions*, 18, New York.
- [4] Sullivan, L. H. (1896). The tall office building artistically considered. In J. M. Stein & K. F. Spreckelmeyer (Eds.), *Classic readings in architecture* (1999). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [5] Avicenna. (1936). *Boundaries or Definitions* (translated by Mohammad Mehdi Foladvand, second edition). Tehran: Soroush Publications.
- [6] Ardalan, Nader, and Bakhtiar, Laleh. (1939). *Sense of Unity: A Mystical Tradition in Iranian Architecture* (translated by Hamid Shahrokh). Tehran: Khak Publications.
- [7] Pazuki, Shahram. (1939). Mystical Knowledge in the Eyes of Mulla Sadra. *Sadra's Memoirs*, 20, 38–45.
- [8] Tagvaei, Vida. (1930). From What Is to the Definition of Architecture. *City Identity*, 7, 75–86.
- [9] Jenks, Charles. (1933). *The Architecture of the Cosmic Leap* (translated by Vahid Ghobadian and Dariush Sattarzadeh). Tabriz: Islamic Azad University, Tabriz Branch.
- [10] Khansari, Mohammad. (1938). *A Brief Course in Formal Logic* (14th edition). Tehran: Tehran University Publications.
- [11] Shaygan, Dariush. (1380). *New Enchantment: The Four-Piece Identity and Mobile Thinking* (translated by Fatemeh Valiani). Tehran: Farzan Rooz.
- [12] Sadr al-Mutal'ahin (Molla Sadra). (1353). *The Supreme Philosophy or the Wisdom of Sadr al-Mutal'ahin: Abridgement and Translation of the Public Affairs and Theology Section of the Book of Travels* (Mohammad Javad Mosleh, Compiled by). Tehran: Tehran University Press.

July. 2026, Tabriz, Iran

- [13] Flamki, Mohammad Mansour. (1381). The Roots and Theoretical Trends of Architecture. Tehran: Faza Publishing House.
- [14] Kapen, P. (1383). Theoretical Foundations of Architecture (translated by Ali Yaran, vols. 1 and 2). Tehran: Islamic Azad University, Sciences and Research Branch.
- [15] Corbin, Henry. (1358). The Land of Heaven: The Human Body on the Day of Resurrection from Tomorrow's Iran to Shiite Iran (translated by Seyyed Zia al-Din Dehshiri). Tehran: Iranian Center for the Study of Cultures.
- [16] Coomaraswamy, Ananda. (2005). Why Should We Exhibit Works of Art? In: Mostafa Dehghan (editor), The New Cup and the Old May. Tehran: Institute for Research and Development of Humanities.
- [17] Mojtahedi, Karim. (2003). Existence and Presence in the Book of Poetry by the Great Molla Sadra. Sadra's Memoirs, 32.
- [18] Norberg-Schultz, Christian. (2002). Architecture: Presence, Language and Place (translated by Alireza Seyyed Ahmadian). Tehran: Memar Publishing Institute.